

INTEGRATING IMAGING TECHNIQUES FOR ASSESSING THE PERFORMANCE OF LARGE COMPOSITES STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

Imaging techniques have the potential to revolutionise our approach to engineering design, offering new insight into material and larger system behaviour over a range of length and time scales. The recent relative reduction in cost of the camera systems and increased processing power to handle images, provides the opportunity for the techniques to be deployed at larger scales and realised industrially. A novel integrated imaging and loading system is under development, known as Structures 2025, funded by the UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council. Structures 2025 comprises a reconfigurable system, which can be used for the testing and assessment of a wide range of structures. It has the potential to revolutionise traditional approaches to structural testing, certification and validation by providing hi-fidelity measurements in a realistic composite structure. In the paper the technical steps to develop Structures 2025 are described along two underpinning cases studies that demonstrate the potential of using such a system on composite structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

The benefits of using imaging to extract a measurement compared to traditional techniques are:

- (i) an entire field can be observed as opposed to a single point (i.e. full-field),
- (ii) the measurement is high resolution, both spatially and temporally, because there are multiple devices in the imaging sensor which can capture data at very high sample rates (frame rates), i.e. data-rich,
- (iii) the field of view is controlled by the optics, which means it can cover multiple scales,
- (iv) imaging is non-contact which means the act of measuring does not modify the measurement obtained.

Thermoelastic stress analysis (TSA) [1] is based on the use of infrared thermography to obtain a small temperature change, associated with the thermoelastic effect, that can be directly related to the stresses. Digital Image Correlation (DIC) [2] tracks features on the surface of a material to establish a displacement field of a component subjected to load, which can then be used to calculate the displacement/strain field. Combining the techniques offers significant benefits. DIC provides the individual strain components but is limited in spatial resolution so areas with high strain gradients, such as around defects, discontinuities and damaged zones are not well-resolved. In contrast TSA has high spatial resolution, provides a direct stress measure, but can only provide the sum of the principal stresses, making it difficult to implement directly in the context of failure criteria. The information provided by the two methods is complimentary, thereby giving independent measurements, which together offer a richer understanding of the mechanical and thermal behaviour of the component or material being tested. The largest benefit in upscaling the use of imaging techniques is in component, element and substructure testing, which is gaining more interest, particularly in composite structures, e.g. [3] [4] to reduce the number of coupon tests required for certification. Therefore, the aim of the present keynote paper is to describe the advances that have allowed the development of structural testing facility predicated on full-field imaging techniques.

Structures 2025 is novel integrated imaging and loading system that is flexible, which can be used for the testing and assessment of a wide range of structures with the potential to revolutionise traditional

approaches to structural testing, certification and validation by providing hi-fidelity measurements in a realistic composite structure. Figure 1 shows a schematic of the elements of Structures 2025. The strong floor is supported by ‘egg-box’ shear wall foundations, which allows a load capacity of 500 kN vertically and 250 kN horizontally in a grid of strong points with a 1 m × 1 m spacing throughout the floor. To simulate realistic service loading conditions computer control systems are used so the load can be applied independently and synchronously, and enable complex loading waveforms for fatigue evaluations. The imaging systems comprise both white light and infrared systems, which allow DIC and TSA to be performed simultaneously using multiple cameras.

Figure 1 Schematic of Structures 2025

The paper reviews progress in a number of areas essential to the development of the Structures 2025 vision:

- Development of low cost multiple camera IR imaging systems for large structures
- Loading configurations to create realistic boundary conditions on sub structure
- Integration of imaging techniques

2 INFRA-RED SYSTEMS

TSA [1] relies on the measurement of the temperature of a component whilst it is undergoing a sinusoidal cyclic loading. The small temperature change resulting from the thermoelastic response is related to the stresses in the principal material directions as follows [1]:

$$\Delta T = -\frac{T_0}{\rho C_p} (\alpha_1 \Delta \sigma_1 + \alpha_2 \Delta \sigma_2) \quad (1)$$

where ΔT is the small temperature change, T_0 is the mean surface temperature, ρ is the density of the material, C_p is specific heat at constant pressure, α is the coefficient of thermal expansion, $\Delta \sigma$ is the stress change and the subscripts 1 and 2 denote the principal material axes.

TSA is commonly applied with cooled infrared (IR) detectors so-called photon detectors. Photon detectors require a cryogenic cooling system that provides low Noise Equivalent Temperature Difference (NETD) of ~20 mK. However, the need for cooling increases the cost of the IR system significantly, makes the detector heavy and bulky, not particularly portable. On the other hand, uncooled IR cameras, i.e. microbolometers, are small robust and lightweight which make them ideal for structural applications. The main limitations of microbolometers are that the NETD is greater (~40 mK) than the photon detectors and more importantly their slow response time means that for specimens subject to

cyclic loading (as used in TSA) an attenuation in output signal occurs. Nevertheless, the cost reduction of one order of magnitude compared with photon detectors, the faster set-up and lighter and more compact nature of bolometers has made them a more attractive proposition for TSA. Essentially the microbolometer behaves as a low-pass filter, hence there is a need for calibration to overcome the filtering effect [5, 6]. It has been shown [7] that when using microbolometers in TSA at different loading frequencies (1 - 11 Hz), there is a significant filtering effect due to the thermal time constant of the detector, which is intrinsic to the sensor material [8]. Therefore, it is necessary to calibrate the measured ΔT at a specific loading frequency to obtain the actual magnitude of ΔT .

The calibration approach has been demonstrated in simple coupons. To assess the effect of the specimen loading frequency on the response, specimens made from materials with known thermoelastic constant ($\alpha/\rho C_p$ - see equation (1)) were chosen. A 316L stainless steel strip of dimensions 237 mm long, 30 mm wide and 2 mm thick, and an aluminium alloy 6081 dogbone type specimen with gauge section 15 mm x 6 mm were used. Both the stainless steel and the aluminium alloy specimens were loaded to achieve three different temperature changes at different loading frequencies (from 0.25 Hz to 11 Hz) and different microbolometer frame rates (6.25 Hz, 12.5 Hz, 25 Hz and 50 Hz). The results obtained from the aluminium and the stainless steel specimens are presented in 2 where ΔT obtained from the bolometer has been normalised by the predicted ΔT so that all the results can be compared. If the bolometer was responding fully to ΔT , all the experiments should have shown a normalised value of 1. However, it can be seen that the bolometer attenuates the temperature change when the loading frequency increases and it can be seen that it does not vary with the frame rate, material or loading amplitude. Therefore, a calibration parameter can be determined and used to provide an accurate ΔT from specimens loaded at loading frequencies from 1 Hz and above, which is necessary to maintain the adiabatic conditions essential for TSA. As an example, calibration parameter versus loading frequency at a frame rate of 50 Hz is presented in Figure 3. The calibration parameter has been determined for 25 Hz, 12.5 Hz and 6.25 Hz frame rates and have the same trend as for 50 Hz frame rate. This demonstrates that the calibration parameter is independent of material, camera frame rate, load level and only dependent on the loading frequency. Hence, microbolometers could be used effectively to apply TSA to a range of composites structures.

Figure 2 Ratio between measured and predicted temperature change on a stainless steel (SS) and aluminium (Al) specimens at different frame rates

Figure 3 Calibration parameter vs loading frequency (LF) at 50 Hz frame rate (SS: 316L stainless steel, Al: aluminium)

3 INTEGRATING DIC WITH TSA

Combining IR thermography and DIC has been carried out successfully, e.g. [9] to measure spatial and temporal distributions of temperatures and displacements simultaneously on E-glass/vinyl ester/balsa wood sandwich composites. TSA and DIC techniques have been successfully applied together to analyse composite components, e.g. [10], but it was necessary to capture the DIC images separately under quasi static conditions and then capture the IR images from cyclic loading conditions to obtain the TSA data. Hence in [11], a procedure was developed that enabled the image capture for the DIC to be synchronised to the load cycle. Although successful, the procedure was cumbersome and

relied on exact timing of the image capture. In [12], a new approach was developed now known as Lock-In DIC (LIDIC), which enables the IR and visible light images to be captured together but without the need to synchronise with the load cycle or synchronise the cameras.

The use of a cyclic load provides an opportunity for filtering, in TSA, a lock-in (LI) amplifier is applied, using a reference signal to reject noise in the temperature measurement. The approach uses the idea of the LI amplifier to filter strains derived from DIC and has the added advantage of improving the strain resolution. However, when employing standard digital cameras for DIC, the additional problem of low sampling rates and the consequent undersampling of the signal of interest, poses an additional challenge. However, through careful selection of loading and sampling frequencies strain changes occurring faster than the available sampling rate can none-the-less be captured accurately. The process is described in detail in [12]. Essentially, the LI amplifier multiplies a measurement signal with a reference signal and then integrates the result over a number of periods. The output is a value proportional to the amplitude of the measurement signal. The effect is like a band pass filter; the larger the number of periods in the analysed signal, the narrower the band pass and the better the noise rejection. For this, it is important that the reference signal has a high signal to noise ratio and that it has exactly the same frequency as the component of the measurement signal of interest.

The implementation of the LI amplifier for DIC can be divided into three parts. First, a series of images of the specimen are recorded while undergoing a cyclic load. A reference signal value is also recorded with each image, usually from the test machine load cell signal generator. The second step is to obtain a corresponding series of strain fields, each calculated relative to the first image in the series. These strain values form the set of measurement signals: one signal for each correlation cell in the DIC. Finally, the reference signal is converted into two reference signals, 90° out of phase with each other, and with their amplitude normalised to 1. The LI algorithm is then implemented using, e.g., Matlab. For this, the strain images are imported into 2D arrays and the amplitude of the strain was obtained for each element, giving an image of strain amplitudes.

A visual comparison of the standard DIC and the LIDIC approaches is presented in Figure 4, where the y-direction strains are shown on disc loaded in 2 point diametral compression, i.e. the Brazilian disc. The image is divided into quarters; the top left shows the results from a static test using one image obtained at -0.5 kN and a second at -9.5 kN to obtain the strain field, the top right shows the result obtained by applying the LI amplifier to obtain the strain amplitude of the disc loaded at 0.75 Hz, the bottom left shows the result loaded at 7.1 Hz (sub-Nyquist sampling) and the bottom right shows the theoretical strains, calculated using an the analytical solution . The difference between the static case and the two dynamic load cases is significant. Especially where the strains are small towards the centre of the disc, these lie significantly below the noise threshold of the DIC calculation. A larger subset size for the DIC size would lower the noise threshold at the expense of spatial resolution.

Figure 4 Strains (ϵ_{yy} – vertical axis) calculated by the standard approach (top left), using the LIDIC applied to a 0.75 Hz loading frequency (top right), using LIDIC applied to a 7.1 Hz loading frequency (bottom left) and the theoretical value (bottom right)

The LIDIC approach has been combined with TSA and during fatigue test track damage growth and in metallic components [13], where an extensive validation was conducted and it was demonstrated that

stress intensity factors could be derived by combining the two techniques. It was Bull et al. [14] who applied TSA and DIC simultaneously to a CFRP spar corner to track damage development of subsurface wrinkles demonstrating the application of TSA and DIC to larger scale composite structure. This work was presented at the previous ICCM conference and a summary is presented in the next section as case study 1.

4 CASE STUDY 1: WING SPAR CORNER

The CFRP test specimen was representative of part of the corner of a wing spar. The component specimen was 300 mm long with a 160 mm limb length. The thickness of the component was ~21 mm along half of the length, with a linear taper that transitioned from 21 to 15 mm along the other half of the length. A wrinkle defect was located along the inner corner. To facilitate TSA and DIC work, a thin layer of matt black spray paint was applied to the inner and outer corners of the component followed fine distribution of white paint speckles. This led to speckle density of ~6 speckles per mm² and an average speckle size of 8.9 pixels per speckle.

The test specimen was loaded in a servo-hydraulic test machine as shown in Figure 5 using a specially design rig that mimicked the in service pressure loading. The rig enabled the transfer of tensile load through the limbs of the test specimen to open the corner of the component, and applied a bending and shear loading to the corner as would be experience under internal pressurisation. The design of the rig enabled unobstructed access for the cameras to study the inner and outer corner of the specimen. Two pairs of Manta white light cameras with Nikon 50 mm f.1.8 prime lenses were placed on either side of the component to capture images for stereo DIC to be conducted on either side of the specimen. A single infrared photon detector camera (Cedip Silver 480M, 320x256-pixel resolution, and sensitivity of 4.2 mK at 25°C) was used to study the inner and outer corner.

The test specimen was loaded in four stages as shown in Figure 6. As the load was increased, images were captured so that DIC could be applied for each load increase. After each loading stage, the specimen was cyclically loaded at 10 ± 5 kN with a frequency of 5 Hz. Both infrared and white light images were captured during the cyclic loading to apply TSA and LIDIC. During the fourth load stage, the specimen failed with a tensile load of 44 kN, by a fast and almost instantaneous subsurface delamination towards the inner corner.

Figure 5 Test rig used to mimic the in service load

Figure 6 Loading stages used for TSA and LIDIC

For the ΔT values obtained from the TSA, after application of the 1st and 2nd load, there was a stress concentration observed at the wrinkle. Comparing the temperature reading from the wrinkle against far field readings indicates a stress concentration factor of approximately 2.8. Similarly, to the TSA, in the $\Delta \epsilon_{yy}$ the presence of the wrinkle was also detectable with the size and shape of the wrinkle matching in DIC and TSA data. Both TSA and LIDIC images are shown in Figure 7 after the third load stage. Initial delaminations were observed close to the wrinkle, in the TSA indicated by a localised region of low ΔT , <0.02 K, as the presence of local delaminations results in a localised reduction of load carrying capability in this region. The presence of delamination initiation was identified as indicated by low local strains surrounding the wrinkle defect, again matching the observations in TSA. After the 4th load,

significant span-wise delamination damage resulted in a significant loss of load carrying capacity in this region and hence a low thermoelastic response covering the full field of view. The work demonstrated that the techniques could be combined and used on composite structures. The outputs from the techniques correlated well with observations of the defect in X-ray computed tomography and the stress concentrations correlated well with those obtained from finite element analysis. Most importantly, the failure load obtained in the experiments correlated practically exactly with that predicted by the finite element modelling. The work in the wing spar has shown it is possible combine TSA and DIC, the next step is to fully integrate the output from the two techniques and combine with models.

Figure 7 Images after application of 3rd loading stage

5 CASE STUDY 2: APPLICATION TO COMPLEX COMPOSITE SUBSTRUCTURE

To move towards a more structural component a T-joint substructure from a wind turbine blade spar was chosen. It is formed by different materials, i.e. wood, resin and glass fibre epoxy composites. The overall dimensions are 400 mm wide, 300 mm height and 50 mm thick as shown in Figure 8a. The joint was loaded at 5 ± 4 kN in a specially designed rig as shown Figure 8b with loading frequencies between 1 and 5 Hz. To perform TSA and LIDIC simultaneously, the surface was first painted with a high emissivity matt black paint to provide a uniform surface emissivity for TSA. Then, white speckles were applied for LIDIC.

Figure 8 Complex composite structure

Figure 9 shows the TSA output for the microbolometer and the LIDIC data integrated at the same scale. The white light cameras have much higher resolution than the microbolometer (10.1 pix/mm vs 2.54 pix/mm). However, DIC and LIDIC relies on tracking subsets of pixels, therefore, the actual resolution of the LIDIC is reduced considerable. In this case, a subset size of 33 pixels and step size of 11 pixels were selected, which gives a spatial resolution of 0.92 subsets/mm. An interpolation procedure to make the resolution of the two image data sets the same was performed and is described in detail in [15] (to be presented at the ICCM22).

The ΔT and the strain changes given in Figure 9 show that at the centre of the T-joint, within the resin pocket, there is a stress concentration of ~ 0.07 K (1) due to a void defect. Additionally, other stress concentration regions (ΔT data) can be seen on the lower part of the flange, at the centre of the grid laminate, at the right corner of the hollow profile and at the boundary between the abachi wood and the web sheets formed of biaxial GFRP. The $\Delta \epsilon_{xx}$ shows the presence of a crack inside the substructure at the boundary between the abachi wood and the resin pocket (2), it is propagating upwards, where the stress concentration (3) was seen in the ΔT field. The $\Delta \epsilon_{xx}$ level of the crack is $>0.1\%$ and it has a length of 70 mm and is 0.7 mm wide. There are strain concentration regions at the top edge and bottom edge of the flange. The $\Delta \epsilon_{xy}$ indicates that the shear strain change affects the abachi wood at a level $>0.1\%$ and the centre right of the T-joint at the web sheets, because the crack is located at this side of the T-joint. The neutral axis (4) of the flange can be observed in the ΔT and $\Delta \epsilon_{xx}$ fields. The TSA data suffers from motion on all the data field that can be seen on the edges, a motion compensation algorithm is needed to compensate for it and will be applied in future experiments once developed. However, the images shown in Figure 12 represent an important first step at of fully integrating TSA and LIDIC data. In [15] it is shown how combining the data provides a useful indicator of the presence of damage.

Figure 9 Integration of TSA and LIDIC

6 CLOSING REMARKS

An over view of the development of the LIDIC and TSA techniques has been provided. It is shown that low cost microbolometers can be used successfully for TSA. It has also been shown that LIDIC can be used process visible light images so that it is not necessary to synchronise data capture either with the load cycle or with the infrared cameras. This means that a low cost methodology has been develop that will allow multiple cameras to be used on large scale structural tests and that the technology underpinning the Structures 2025 concept has been demonstrated.

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